

Dissemination method for sustainable soybean production areas in Jambi

Lutfi Izhar^{1*}, Yardha¹ and Salwati¹

¹Jambi Assessment Institute for Agricultural Technology (AIAT)

Jl. Samarinda Paal 5, Kota Baru, Jambi. 36128

*Corresponding author: lutfiizhar@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

The challenge of agricultural development in the future is increasingly complex, including how to meet the needs and food self-sufficiency. The current agricultural problems are limitations of land resources, water, infrastructure, production facilities and infrastructures, access to financial and institutional. These problems result in weakness of the quantity and quality of agricultural products. One of the efforts to minimize these problems is the development of comprehensive integrated program in agricultural area and the implementation of the various relevant department/agency as well as participation of farmers. The development of soybean area in Jambi province was conducted in Tebo Regency. The each of area covers 2.500 hectare since 2015 until 2017. The activity was conducted through coordination and integration program from local government, department and agency related to commodity that was developed from upstream to downstream. Conservation agriculture, new soybean variety application, balance fertilizer recommendation, on farm training and good agricultural practices were applied during dissemination processes. Due to application of GAP, soybean productivities become increasing twenty percent.

Key words : soybean, accompaniment, production, Tebo regency

INTRODUCTION

Agricultural sector is one of the crucial strategies for future Indonesian economic growth. The strategic role of agriculture can be realized through integrated agricultural area development; the establishment of capital; the provision of foodstuffs, industrial raw materials, feed and bioenergy; the absorbent of labour; the source of foreign exchange; the source of income; and also the preservation of environment through environmentally friendly farming practices (Dimiyati et al. 1991; Indonesian Food Crop Directorate General, 2014).

The various strategic roles of agriculture meant with the purpose of national economic development that is increasing the welfare of Indonesian people, accelerating economic growth, reducing poverty, providing employment, and maintaining the balance of natural resources and environment

(Indonesian Agriculture Ministry, 2011). An inevitability that the agricultural sector should be encouraged an increase in quantity and quality from upstream to downstream. One of strategic agricultural commodity in Indonesia is soybean (Cipto and Sarjoni, 2013)

Soybean self-sufficiency target is the main program of the Ministry of agriculture in the period of 2015 till 2019. As the mainstay commodity that is programmed by Government, the role of soybean is strategic enough and it is a commodity with high economic value. Besides being the main source of carbohydrates and soybean protein, Soybean is also a raw material for household industry. In the last few years, the demand for soybean continues to rise along with increasing rate of population growth and increasing demand to feed (Indonesian Agency for Agriculture Research and Development, 2012).

The area of soybean crop in Jambi Province reaches 1,877 hectares, with 2,372 tons of dry beans production (Statistical Bureau for Jambi Province, 2015). Soybean plants spread in 9 districts/cities. The largest of soybean cultivation and the area of soybean production center in Jambi Province are Tebo and East Tanjung Jabung Regency with widely each 16.89 percent hectares and 42.83 percent. Whereas, the productivity of this commodity is still low 13.40 ton/ ha (Jambi Agricultural Provincial Report, 2015).

The Low productivity is caused by inferior management of soybean commodities that have not integrated and need more assessment in the aspect of technical and non - technical farming systems (Adie and Krisnawati, 2013). In account for that, the Indonesian Government, made a regulation by the Minister of Agriculture number 50/Permentan/140/8/2012 about comprehensive escort for agricultural development area. Tebo Regency was selected as a development area of soybean. Hence, the purpose of this paper was to describe the implementation of agricultural technology innovation acquaintance with dissemination technique for soybean areas in Tebo regency.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The development of agricultural areas is implemented by conducting activities in the field in the form of demplot units which is areas for integrated agribusiness development (Jambi Development Agency. 2011). The holistic demplot and existed unit includes aspects of production technology improvement, post harvest, processing of results, empowerment aspects of farming communities, aspects of development and strengthening of agribusiness support facilities. The pilot unit also serves as a field laboratory for an assessment activity in order to improve technological and institutional persuading in supporting agribusiness efforts, in anticipation of vigorous and

socio-economic changes in the dynamic environment. A pilot unit plan with a 2 ha pilot area as a field laboratory, representing over 100 ha of expanse area.

The scope of activities was by demonstration of soybean technological innovation, dissemination accomplishments, institutional institutionalization of farming, institutional financing, harvest and post harvest technologies, market and integration of programs / activities from relevant offices / agencies in a region.

The activity was conducted in Serai Serumpun Sub-district, Tebo, from January to December 2016. The plan action has been developed and established by the local agricultural Institution, cooperation farmers group and agricultural field officer (PPL). Preparation of the location of activities includes the selection of overlays as needed, and carried out with farmer groups.

Stages of activities carried out were: (1) Initiation model; (2) Technological escort (cultivation technology / seed breeding, harvesting and post-harvesting of soybean); (3). Field Dem Plot Observations made on the growth and development stage of plants. The data collected both primary data and secondary data was processed by using simple tabulation. While the analysis is descriptive analysis of quantitative and qualitative descriptive.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Soybean is one of the potential cereals crops developed in Tebo Regency. Currently, Tebo District is one of the national soybean development area and also soybean belt areas (Bappeda and BPS Tebo. 2014). The soybean area of harvested, production and productivity over the past five years, can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Soybean yield areas, production and productivity in the years of 2009-2015

Years	Soybean Yield areas (Ha)	Production (Ton)	Productivity (Ton/Ha)
2009	1,567	2,295	1.46
2010	847	1,240	1.46
2011	611	869	1.42
2012	611	869	1.42
2013	804	1,031	1.28
2014	1,683	2,212	1.29
2015	1,729	2,310	1.34

Source: Statistical Bureau for Tebo Municipality, 2016

Development of soybeans the year of 2016 was the largest areas located in Tebo District with an area of more than 2500 ha. While, the selected area as demonstration plot (dem-plot) area was owned by BP3K and still located in

Sekutur Jaya village, Serai Serumpun sub-district (Graph 1), with latitude line 1° 15' 6" and longitude 102° 20' 6". Land available more than 5 ha. Soybean varieties of Grobogan and Anjasmoro were cultivated on the demonstration plot.

On field action and advisory activities by AIAT Jambi which has been determined development area in Serai Serumpun sub-district with a total area of 12,000 ha available, current improvement of at least 2,000 ha. In 2016 Serai Serumpun area was one of the driest areas in Jambi affecting agricultural optional activities.

Graph 1. Tebo Municipality Administration Map and Serai Serumpun District Map

Mentoring was initially done by discussing with the board (local agricultural officers) and some representatives from the Joint Farmer Group (*Gapoktan*) of "Mandiri Bersama" and the working group that was directed by Irmawan S. Ginting AmK, Secretary M. Yusuf and involving the head of BP3K Bapak Tanius and the Corporate Workers' Jaya headed by Sopyah Hadi, Al Fadli Secretary and Treasurer Bapak Saronto. Corporate Group comprehend of Farmer Groups, with members of more than 150 farmers.

Along with those farmers' groups, the application of several components of soybean innovation cultivation technology based on locally integrated crop management guidance can be seen in Table 2. The basic component was the application of new soybean improved varieties that all farmers during 2016 planting season use Grobogan variety, high quality seed and labeled from soybeans seed breeder that are located only about 30 Km from the village, additional *rhizobium* for soil, integrated pest management and plant spacing or population settings (Muzainah and Subandi. 2013). While on the

choice of components such as land processing was done by all farmers, fertilization based on needs/recommendation done if the fertilizer is available by all farmers, the use of ameliorant and organic material obtained from the burning side of the plant or when the rest of the plant remains placed in cultivation land, timely harvest and irrigation if drought with the assumption that water sources remain.

Table 4. Adoption Soybean Local Specific Agricultural Innovation Technology in the Areas that were Assisted by AIAT Jambi in Tebo Regency.

No	Technology components	Number of selected farmer (group)	Number of selected farmers (persons)	Number of selected farmers who follow the technologies (Persons)	Percentage (%)
Basic Components					
1	New Variety Recommendation	8	150	150	100
2	High Quality Seed and Labeled	8	150	150	100
3	Additional Rhizobium Application for newly soybean areas or sleeping land areas	8	150	120	80
4	Soybean Population arrangement (350.000-500.000 plant/ha)	8	150	150	100
5	Integrated Pest and Disease treatments	8	150	75	50
Alternative Components					
6	Land Preparation	8	150	150	100
7	Fertilizers application based on plant needs	8	150	100	70
8	Additional Organic Compound	4	70	50	40
9	Ameliorant application for acidic dry soils	8	150	100	70
10	Watering/Irrigating in crises periods	2	40	40	100
11	Precise Harvest and Post-Harvest activities	8	150	120	80

Activities that support the assistance is the institutional activities of farmers that still need to be addressed, especially marketing institutions, production, and post-harvest. The farmer institution is referred to a farming institution located in the local area, in the form of membership organization or cooperatives i.e. farmers belonging to the cooperation group (Uphoff, 1992).

This institution includes a broad understanding, including the notion of peasant organizations, as well as the "rules of the game" or rules of conduct that determine patterns of action and social relations, including social unity-the social unity which is a concrete form of an institution (Mosher, 1991).

Capacity building of farmers and institutional groups of farmers is needed in an effort to improve the competitiveness of farmers in the development of agribusiness system in Indonesia. This effort is increasingly needed in the face of the era of globalization and free trade. The capacity of farmers can increase in line with their participation in farmer institutions. The capacity of farmers and their participation in farmer institutions will encourage institutional capacity to be more effective (Branson and Douglas,1983).

Agricultural institutions also have a strategic point (entry point) in moving the agribusiness system in the countryside. Therefore, all resources in rural areas need to be directed/prioritized in order to improve the professionalism and bargaining position of farmers (farmer groups). Currently farmers' portraits and farmer institutions in Indonesia are recognized and still not as expected (Elizabeth and Darwis. 2003; Suradisastra, 2016).

The institutional role in developing agricultural sector in tebo district has mainly seen in food crops activities, especially soybean. the role of the institution is very prominent in increasing food production and marketing the results. This condition shows the significance of institutional empowerment in the acceleration of rural agricultural sector development has begun to look its role (Yardha et al.2013).

This is in line with the results of various observations which conclude that if the agricultural development initiative is implemented by an institution or organization, in which individual individuals with an organizational soul combine their knowledge in the planning and implementation stages of the initiative then the chances of successful agricultural development become greater (De los Reyes, and Jopillo,1986; Albrecht, H. 1989).

The result of this facilitation activity from the institutional aspect shows that most of the respondents joined the institutional organization, almost 100% of the respondents said they participated in the institutional organization, and joined the cooperatives, farmer groups and farmer group associations. The biggest reasons to join in institutional organizations such as farmer groups and cooperatives are due to facilitate them to get information, add insight and simplify in marketing concerns (Pakpahan, 1990).

CONCLUSIONS

The development of the soybean cultivation area has been planned for 3 years starting 2015 - 2017. Assistance and development of the area is only

started in 2016 in the soybean production center of Sekutur Jaya village, Serai Serumpun sub-district, Tebo regency. Assistance was done through Field School Assistance, Introduction of soybean commodity technology innovation from upstream - downstream and engineering of farmer supporting institution, supported by dissemination of technology component in the form of leaflet distribution, booklet, brochure and other technological innovations. At the next mentoring activity besides price and marketing as become the focus of activity, innovation technology for soybean harvest, harvest handling method and post-harvest should be deeply monitored.

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